

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

FUNCTIONS AND ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE OF STATE ADMINISTRATION

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Abstract

The question of the structure of state power is the question of its internal structure, of the elements of which it consists. It seems that the structure of state power must be considered from different positions, from different points of view. This will allow you to get a deeper understanding of the state power itself and the elements that make it up. Starting to study the content and features of the public administration of the Republic of Kazakhstan, it is necessary, first of all, to determine what is governance? This term has become a universal means of characterizing a certain type of activity, i.e. a set of actions performed in order to achieve the relevant socially significant goals. Public administration is the most important legal institution designed to exercise executive power. Public administration is a purposeful organizing, sub-legislative, executive-administrative and regulatory activity of the system of state executive bodies that perform the functions of public administration on the basis of and in pursuance of laws in various sectors and areas of socio-cultural, economic and administrative-political construction.

Keywords: state, administration, power, structure of state power, public administration

Introduction

The definition of the concept of "public administration" can be approached from different points of view. Sometimes management is defined as such a state activity that is neither justice nor lawmaking, that is, management is the activity of the state or other subjects of state (public) power, carried out outside the boundaries of lawmaking and justice. This is the so-called negative definition of public administration.

Public administration is the most important legal institution designed to exercise executive power. From an organizational and functional point of view, public administration is an imperious ordering influence of the subject of management (the state and its special bodies or officials) on the objects of management (society, citizens, etc.). Public administration is a purposeful organizing, by-law, executive-administrative and regulatory activity of the system of state executive bodies that perform the functions of public administration (due to the functions of the state itself) on the basis of and in pursuance of laws in various sectors and areas of socio-cultural, economic and administrative political construction.

The theory of administrative law has developed two approaches to the definition of public administration, taking into account the above provisions.

1. Public administration in a broad sense is the regulatory activity of the state as a whole (the activities of representative authorities, executive authorities, prosecutors, courts and other bodies). Public administration in a broad sense characterizes all the activities of the state in terms of organizing the impact of special subjects of law on social relations. The functions of public administration, such as the selection, placement, certification of personnel, accounting and control, the use of coercive and incentive measures, disciplinary action, forecasting, planning, coordination, financing, and so

on, to one degree or another, are carried out by many state bodies: the court, the prosecutor's office, representative public authorities. They exercise control over the activities of their formations, committees and commissions, hear the report of the head of administration, select personnel for work in the apparatus of these bodies.

2. Public administration in the narrow sense is an administrative activity, that is, the activity of the executive bodies of state power both at the level of the Republic of Kazakhstan and its subjects. In administrative law, as a rule, the concept of public administration is considered to a greater extent in a narrow sense.

Public administration in the narrow sense refers to the practical activities of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan. The bodies exercising the functions of public administration also include local self-government bodies, local administration, its bodies and structural subdivisions.

Institutions exercising public administration in the Republic Kazakhstan:

1. President of the Republic of Kazakhstan (head of state) - elected through direct elections by secret ballot for a period of 7 years. It defines the main directions of domestic and foreign policy, represents Kazakhstan both within the country and in the international arena. It ensures the coordinated functioning of all branches of government and the responsibility of all authorities to the people. During his term of office, the President is obliged to suspend membership in any political party.

2. The Parliament of the Republic of Kazakhstan, consisting of two chambers: the Senate (upper) and the Majilis (lower) - the legislative body) The Senate is elected for 6 years, the Mazhilis - for 5 years. The Senate is formed on the basis of indirect suffrage; it includes 2 people from each region, city of republican

significance and the capital of Kazakhstan, plus 15 deputies appointed by the President of Kazakhstan. The Majilis consists of 107 deputies, of which 98 deputies are elected through direct elections held in administrative-territorial constituencies, and 9 are elected by the Assembly of the People of Kazakhstan.

3. The Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan - the Prime Minister, Deputy Prime Ministers, heads of ministries.

4. The system of judicial bodies (the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the Supreme Court of the Republic of Kazakhstan, local courts - judicial authorities).

The concept of public administration includes the most important organizational and legal categories that are manifested in managerial relations: state administrative activity is the implementation by the subjects of executive power, as well as other parts of public administration, of the functions of public administration.

The question of the structure of state power is the question of its internal structure, of the elements of which it consists. It seems that the structure of state power must be considered from different positions, from different points of view. This will allow you to get a deeper understanding of the state power itself and the elements that make it up.

First of all, consider the structure of state power from the point of view of the structure of power in general. At the same time, we will abstract from the fact that power is in constant motion, functioning, and we will consider it as if at rest, in statics. In the scientific literature, with this approach, it is customary to single out two structural elements of power: will and force. Will is the defining element of power. Any power is always a manifestation of someone's will: the will of an individual, a group of people, a class, a people, etc. To rule means to put your will into practice, to impose it on someone, to subordinate it to someone. State power is also someone's will. At present, they believe that this is either the will of the people, or the will of certain classes, or the will of some social groups.

The second structural element of power is strength. Strength, as it were, reinforces the will, contributes to its implementation. Without power, the will is not able to assert itself, not able to influence the behavior of others. The strength of power can be expressed in its authority, in ideological influence, in coercion, in violence. The power of state power is most clearly manifested in state bodies, primarily in enforcement agencies - the army, police and others. When the authority of the state power is not enough to approve the state will, as a rule, the mechanism of state coercion comes into play in the person of the relevant bodies.

The state is the main institution of the political system of society, which manages it, protects its economic and social structure.

The state has a monopoly on coercion of the entire population within a certain territory, the right to implement domestic and foreign policy on behalf of the entire society, the exclusive right to issue laws and regulations binding on the entire population, the right to levy taxes and other fees. The state represents as a whole a form of organization of the whole society.

The independent influence of the state on the main spheres of society is very significant and can contribute to the development of social relations, or vice versa, hinder it. As the life of a state-organized society becomes more complicated, the role of this influence increases. It is especially noticeable in transit societies that are making the transition from one socio-economic system to another. This can be seen in the examples of the Republic of Kazakhstan and other sovereign independent states formed on the basis of the former Soviet socialist republics and making the transition from communist and command-administrative to democratic and market relations and management methods.

And in these conditions, the issues of increasing the efficiency of state administration are coming to the fore, which, by the way, have been and remain today the main ones in the life of society, both on a national and regional scale. Much depends here on the correct understanding and consideration of the relationship, ensuring the dialectical interaction of politics and economics in the process of government. This problem is intensifying especially in a country that has taken the path of modernization and reforms. It requires constant improvement of the methods of public administration of the economic and social spheres, the introduction and development of effective forms of involving the citizens of the country in governance, the expansion and deepening of democratic principles in the development of the country. The success of socio-political, legal and economic reforms, as well as the effectiveness of local government and self-government in general, depends both on people - members of societies, and on the individual at the helm of the state.

Labor, material and spiritual production, distribution are impossible without a certain organization, order, division of labor, establishment of the place and functions of a person in society, carried out with the help of management. Both the social behavior of people and social relations in general are necessarily subject to management. Each society always makes certain demands on a person, social groups and associations for the fate of the country.

One of the main goals that they set for themselves is to attract attention and invite specialists to a comprehensive study of the problems of public administration.

The question of the state belongs to the category of central questions of the socio-political life of society. The fact is that in the political system of society, the state performs the main function, since it is from the system. Therefore, it is precisely the high socio-political activity of the state, the most complete embodiment in the structure and functions of state bodies of the specific features of the political system. That is why the state, as an effective weapon for the realization of political will, has constantly aroused and continues to arouse the close attention of thinkers at all times.

State formations are closely interconnected with the history of mankind. The development of statehood in the history of civilization is very rich and problematic and has great cognitive significance. The history of the state, in essence, is the history of a

particular country, the fate of its population, because statehood is the subjectivity of the people fixed in power structures, since what the people are, such is the state power.

It should also be noted that the theoretical issues that characterize the origin, role and place of the state in the life of society have solid ideological layers, a critical rethinking of which is necessary in order to have a scientifically based, political analysis of these issues.

Conclusion

In the history of social thought, the change of paradigms was most accurately and directly recorded in the development of theoretical issues of the state.

If we talk about the concept of the state, then, first of all, it is important to note that the term "state" in modern political and everyday vocabulary is used mostly to refer to the socio-economic and political community of people living on a common territory. And in this regard, the term "state" is close in meaning to the term "country". And such an interpretation of the state for ordinary consciousness is very characteristic. And there are good reasons for this. The fact is that, in principle, a state can be called a country where there is

power recognized by people and uniting them into social integrity.

If we talk about the function of the state, then, first of all, it should be noted that in determining the function of the state, we must always be guided by the general role of the state in the life of society. And here the unifying role of the state comes to the fore, it unites the community of people into a single whole, synthesizes their interests, forces them to comply with common norms and thereby forms a certain geopolitical integrity.

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